

**Promotion of Green Electricity: Legal and Political Perspectives
(in Turkish)**

Theme: Energy, European Research Area and SSH Aspects

Çağdaş Onur Artantaş
Moderator: Emel Semiz

Live Seminar Time and Date: 12:00-13:00 (Turkish time / GMT + 3)

Friday, April 22, 2022

Register at: <https://forms.gle/jePtB2d4SkqrRf337>

Moderation: Emel Semiz

Registration for live seminar closes at 20:00, Thursday, 21 April 2022: To receive the link to the live seminar you must register by 20:00, Thursday 21 April 2022.

Abstract: It is becoming increasingly crucial to increase the share of green electricity in the electricity mix in light of the UN SDGs and the Paris Agreement. The increase in the share of green electricity contributes to GHG emission reduction, environmental protection, and the construction of the circular economy. However, the growth in green electricity generation is not a process without concerns. Problems suchlike, inter alia, rise in demand for commodities, adverse effects on the current account balance, increased land use, and destabilization of the grid should be taken into account.

To promote the transition to green electricity, governments utilize a set of subsidies. In this presentation, Dr. Artantaş will first examine the main tools of fiscal or regulatory promotion of green electricity. Then, will present the central arguments in the legal literature regarding the position of green electricity promotion in WTO, EU, and Turkish law and discuss their political standings. Finally, he will provide my legislation and policy proposals for the sustainable growth of the green electricity sector.

Speaker:

Onur Çağdaş Artantaş: Dr. Artantaş obtained his LL.B. in 2012 and public law LL.M. in 2016 from Ankara University. He finalized his Ph.D. at Bucerius Law School in Hamburg with a "Magna cum laude" in 2021, with a dissertation dealing with green electricity promotion in Germany and Turkey. He has been working as a research assistant at Hacettepe University Faculty of Law, Administrative Law Department, since 2013.

About SolarTwins-TEKPOL Pizza Seminars: The path to a prosperous, sustainable, and secure Turkey includes a Clean Energy Transition (CET) and Green Economy Transition (GET). Many of the largest challenges to be solved to realize these transitions lie at the intersection of technology and policy. Some of these challenges are unique to a specific technology, while others are cross-cutting challenges that underpin the competitiveness of Turkey's Research and Innovation (R&I) ecosystem. This SolarTwins-TEKPOL Pizza Seminar series aims to provide a scientific forum to increase awareness of these challenges and contribute to the co-creation of solutions to overcome these challenges. This series is designed as a part of SolarTwins Project Joint Research Line 9: Social Aspects of Sustainable Energy Transitions

About SolarTwins: SolarTwins is a European Union Horizon 2020 (H2020) project coordinated by ODTÜ-GÜNAM through METU with CIEMAT-PSA (Spain) and DLR (Germany) as partners. The objectives of the SolarTwins project are to

1. Step-up the scientific excellence of the Concentrating Solar Thermal (CST) Research Division ODAK of ODTÜ-GÜNAM through capacity building activities in collaboration with the globally leading CST institutions CIEMAT-PSA and DLR.
2. Strengthen METU, ODTÜ-GÜNAM, and Turkey's horizontal Research and Innovation (R&I) Capacities.

About METU TEKPOL: Science and Technology Policy Studies (STPS) program was founded in 1997 at the Middle East Technical University with the explicit objective to supply science and technology policy related human capital for the government bodies, agencies and other related organizations and to conduct research in science, technology and innovation policy issues. It has organic relations with the Research Center for Science and Technology Policies. Education and research elements integrate under METU-TEKPOL. TEKPOL is the only academic unit in Turkey that concurrently coordinates education and research activities. It operates M.Sc. and Ph.D. programs in science technology policy studies at the Graduate School of Social Sciences. TEKPOL also conducts interdisciplinary research on science and technology policy issues with the aim of addressing societal challenges.

PROGRAMME:

Date	Speaker, Institution	Seminar Title
15 April 2022	Arda MEVLÜTOĞLU, Kubilay YILDIRIM and Semih AKÇOMAK	TOGG and Beyond (in Turkish) – Panel
22 April 2022	Onur Çağdaş ARTANTAŞ	Promotion of Green Electricity: Legal and Political Perspectives (in Turkish)
29 April 2022	Serdar TÜRKELİ	Technological change and non-intervention, novel indicators and non-measurement (in Turkish)
13 May 2022	Barbel EPP	Cost Trends for Commercial and Industrial Solar Heat
20 May 2022	Pınar DERİN GÜRE	Gender and social sciences involvement in technology development projects in energy (in Turkish)
27 May 2022	Şuhsnaz YILMAZ ÖZBAĞCI	Energy Security Challenges: Assessing Turkey's Role in Changing Regional Dynamics (in Turkish)
3 June 2022	Derek BAKER	ODAKTR: Concentrating Solar Thermal (CST) as a key enabling technology for Turkey's Clean Energy Transition.
10 June 2022	Christian OLTRA	Introducing SSH aspects of Energy Transitions
17 June 2022	Sara Banu AKKAŞ and Zelal ÖZDEMİR	METU in New European Research Area (in Turkish)
24 June 2022	Seven AĞIR	AgroPV Potential, Opportunities and Barriers in Turkey: A Preliminary Evaluation From Social Sciences Perspective (in Turkish)

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